

Impact of Transformational Leadership on Deviant Workplace Behavior in Pakistani Public Organizations

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Abstract

this study investigated the impact of Transformational Leadership on deviant workplace behavior in Pakistani public organizations. The results were analyzed from a sample of 380 employees belonging to 20 Public organizations of the province of Punjab Pakistan were selected for questionnaire survey. SPSS-21 and Smart PLS packages are employed to analyze the quantitative data. Partial least squares method of structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM) is adopted for the testing of hypotheses. Results revealed significant relationship and supported the hypothesized the direct negative impact of transformational leadership on deviant workplace behavior. This research paper is a pioneer work in the context of public sector of Pakistan and it is an addition to the existing literature on supporting theories of transformational leadership i.e. Social Learning Theory and Social Exchange Theory. This research also provides new directions in this area, by encouraging new debate about the role of transformational leadership in order to control deviant workplace behavior in the public organizations.

Key words: Deviant Workplace Behavior, Transformational Leadership, Public Organizations.

INTRODUCTION

Unfortunately, Pakistan is one of the developing country which facing the serious problem of deviance workplace behaviour of employees in public organizations since its independence in 1947 (Bashir, Nasir, Qayyaum & Bashir, 2012, p.241; Nadeem, Ahmad, Ahmad, Batool & Shafiq, 2015). Public organizations of Pakistan derived inheritance from colonial system of 18th century but after passing 70 years of independence could not incept its indigenous practices to run the public machinery for managing people and resources of the country (Nadeem et al. 2015; Bashir et al. 2012). Public sector is rife with corruption from top to bottom (Nadeem et al. 2015). Every cog of public administration machinery is reflected counterproductive behavior (Yousaf, Zafar, & Abi Ellahi, 2014) or anti-social behavior either financially corrupt or ethically deviant (Nasir & Bashir 2012).

It is common understanding that in Pakistani public organizations controlled, managed, and regulated (Nadeem et al. 2015) and operated by government, either autonomous, or semi-autonomous are characteristically ailing with deviance behavior at workplace of the public employees (Bashir, Nasir, Qayyaum & Bashir, 2012, p.241). In addition, these days, an unethical and deviant workplace behavior is an emerging issue/problem in the organizations (Usmani, Kalpina, & Husain, 2013) and widespread problem in most of Pakistani organizations (Fatima, Atif, saqib & Haider 2012) but remain unexplored (Bashir, Nasir, Saeed & Ahmed 2011). Moreover, favoritism, nepotism and cronyism are also the major causes of deviant workplace behavior in Pakistani public organizations (Bashir et al. 2011). The whole operation of public administration in Pakistan is trapped in red tape that affects the behavior of the employees towards resigned satisfaction (Quartulain & Khan, 2013). Pakistani public organizations facing the problem of lack of effective leadership to control and manage this organization.

The present study focuses to explore the role of transformational leadership to control DWB. Leadership plays a vital role to manage and control employee's deviance behaviour at workplace (Maher & Youssef 2016). Lack of

moral leadership in organization may also because of employees' unethical behavior (Maher & Youssef 2016). Transformational leadership is an ideal leadership elegant that advocates for positive changes in individuals and social systems (Zhang, 2016).

Literature Review and Framework

Deviant Workplace Behavior (DWB)

Deviant workplace behavior (DWB) has been studied under different terms such as retaliation and dysfunctional behavior, organizational misbehavior (Vardi & Wiener, 1996) and counterproductive workplace behavior (Fox, Spector, & Miles, 2001). In the words of Robinson and Greenberg, (1998 pp.3) "there is no common definition regarding workplace deviance that is generally agreed upon" due to initial stage of research area and cited the definition of two eminent scholars who have elaborate this construct of deviant workplace behavior (DWB), operationalized it and key dimension as well as recognized its boundaries (Javed et al. 2014). Eminent research scholars Robinson and Bennett, (1995) are defined Deviance workplace behavior (DWB) as "a voluntary behavior engaged by employee that is contrary to the significant organizational norms and it is considered as a threat to the well-being of an organization and/or its members". Earlier researchers have given different expressions to the term deviance workplace behavior such as counterproductive workplace behavior (Mangione & Quinu, 1975), antisocial behavior (Giacalone & Greenberg, 1997) organizational misbehavior (Ackyrod & Thompson 1999), workplace sabotage (Analoui, 1995; Harris & Ogbonna, 2002), worker resistance (Thompson & Ackroyd, 1995), dysfunctional behaviour (Griffin, O'Leary Kelly & Collins, 1998), and non-complaint behavior (Puffer, 1987) among others, "Bad Behavior" in Organizations (Griffin, & Lopez (2005). According to Greenberg, (1997) "anti-social behavior" that is defined as "any behavior that brings harm or is intended to bring harm to the organization and its employees or its stakeholders" In the words of Robinson and Morrison, (1995) "workplace deviance" that is defined as "voluntary behavior of organizational members that violates significant organizational norms and in so doing, threatens the well-being of the organization and/its members".

Deviant workplace behaviors (DWB) of employees are directly harmful to the organization or to other employees in the organization (Spector et al. 2006) that can range from relatively minor to very serious (Kanten & Ülker, 2013). Griffin and Lopez (2004) noted that all individuals who enter to working organizations have the potential to exhibit this destructive behavior that categories, minor and major deviance. The first, minor, production deviance (Robinson & Betnnet, 1995), working slow intentionally, avails excessive breaks (Bashir et al. 2012), gossiping on non-work topics with coworkers during official working hours, late arrival at workplace and leave office early, day dreaming while on job (Nasir & Bashir, 2012) and involved in cyber loafing (Lim, 2002). The second major, production deviance as theft from organization, do slow work to obtain unnecessary due overtime, without receiving permission to use photocopy machines for personnel purpose, as well as taking office supplies or equipment at home (Anjum & Pervaiz, 2013; Spector and Fox, 2005). On the other hand, interpersonal deviance, has also two categories, minor and major, the first, political deviance is making fun, deal rudely and blaming to coworkers for mistakes did on job, disobeying supervisor's directions and instructions (Robbinson & Betnnett, 1995) the second, personal aggression, (major) such as cursing, humiliating, bullying or stalking and saying hurtful things to coworkers and assaulting with injury to coworkers too (Brown 2008).

Demission of Deviant Workplace Behavior

Demission of deviant workplace behavior contain the individual negative acts at workplace such as abuse against others/bullying, withdrawal, theft, misuse of time and resources , sabotage, production deviance withdrawal and kickback (Bashir et al. 2012; Spector et al. 2006)

Abuse against others/bullying

Abuse or bullying means an act towards coworkers as well as organizational members are treating and handling them violently (Kohut, 2007). Abuse or bullying consists of overt harmful behaviors of an employee (Izawa, Kodama, & Nomura, 2006). Eminent scholars Spector, Fox, Penney, Bruursema, Goh, and Kessler, (2006) asserts that abuse is an act to harm the follow workers. Unpleasant comments are the main cause of abuse at workplace (Contin, & Magley, 2003). Verbal aggression is constitute abuse (Porath & Erez, 2009). "Bullying" at work place leads to abuse (Monks, Smith, Naylor, Barter, Ireland, and Iain Coyne, 2009). Moreover, "bullying" that means an act of dogged (Georgakopoulos, Wilkin, & Kent, 2011). In the words of Oghojafor, Muo and Olufayo (2012) "abusive, intimidating or insulting behavior, abuse of power or unfair punishment which upsets, threatens, humiliates the recipient, undermining their self-confidence, reputation and ability to perform".

Withdrawal

Withdrawal is another dimension of deviant workplace behaviors and intentions of employees Spector et al. (2006). Withdrawal studied comprehensively in the organizational behavior, human resources management and management field but remained below study (Carragher & Buckley, 2008). Withdrawals are negative behaviors that mitigate intentional amount of working time than the required time by the organization (Spector et al. 2006). Eminent researcher Koslowsky, (2000) pointed out that withdrawal behavior may be means of coping with conflicting work and non-work obligations. In U.S. organizations costing loss of estimated \$50 billion annually and responsible for about a 20 percent of failure of businesses due withdrawal behaviour and 33 percent to 75 percent of all employees at workplace have engaged in other type of behaviors such as withdrawal, abuse, theft, sabotage and production deviance (Coffin, 2003; Koslowsky, (2000) and cyber loafing (Lim, 2012). Withdrawal behavior of employee at workplace deteriorated the overall performance of the organization (Spector et al. 2006) and withdrawal behaviors of employee consume almost 15% of an organization's payroll Globally (Faulk & Hicks, 2015).

Theft

Theft is stealing of the physical property or assets from organization (Chen & Spector, 1992). Theft Intentionally harm to organization by employees (Niehoff & Paul, 2000) for satisfaction of their instrumental motives (Spector et al. 2006). Another study of Galperin, (2002) recorded that theft as one of the aspects of deviant behavior instigate employee towards the breach of the organizational norms. Theft or stealing can take different kinds i.e. stealing merchandise, misleading records, pilferage, overcharging and short-changing, deception, payroll fraud and stealing cash and voiding a sale etc. (Gabbidon et al. 2006; Mishra & Prasad, 2006) , According to the Shulman Center for Compulsive Theft and Spending (2007), "employee theft is the fastest growing crime in America. Seventy-five percent of employees steal from workplace and most do so repeatedly". Appelbaum, Cottin, Pare, and Shapiro, (2006) defined theft as "theft or unauthorized appropriation of company property by employees either for one's own use or for sale to another". In addition, Hollinger and Adams (2010) reported in US, approximately \$15.9 billion loss retailers attributed about 45% of their inventory shortage during 2010, which was representing, because of employee's theft. Employee's theft, stealing and occurrence of fraud in an organization are generally reported in each organization either public or private in Pakistan (Bashir et al. 2012; Nasir & Bashir, 2012).

Misuse of Time and Resources

A study of Bashir et al. (2012) have investigated that another dimensions of misuse of official time and resource of public organization and pointed out that the public employees carry out personal business during official timings, taking longer lunch/pray break and use unauthorized organization resources of the public organizations such as making long call personal calls from official telephone and playing games on official computer and chatting and gossiping during official working hours (Gruys,1999; Gruys & Sackett,2003; Spector et al., 2006; Lim, 2002). In current eras, numerous technological advancement inspired other imperative changes has been observed (Brkic & Aleksic, 2016) due to prompt development and innovation of information

technologies as well as internet open door of different type deviance in organization(Lim,2002). Cyber loafing is one of them and best example of misuse of time and resources. However, in today's modern business world, it is practically impossible to work without computers equipment's and internet connection (Derina & Gökçeb 2016). It is pertinent to mention that approximately \$120 billion dollars cost on sickness absenteeism sustained by U.S. organization/institutions in overall expenses and this dollar amount has persisted over the past decade (Biron & Bamberger, 2012).

Production Deviance

In the words of Spector, et al. (2006) production deviance is another important the demission of deviant workplace behavior (DWB). In this category of deviance behavior, the employee intentionally hampering quantity and quality of work and affect organizational productive and efficiency (Hollinger & Clark, 1982). Job tasks are not perform or failure to perform in proper way effectively (Hollinger, 1986). In this ways, the employee intentionally slow down the quantity and quality of work that affects the efficiency and productive of the organization (Hollinger & Clark 1982; Gruys & Sackett 2003). It is also a serious dimension of deviant workplace behavior; if employee deliberately creating problems and hurdles against success of the organization, ultimately it can affects the organizational performance (Coffin, 2003) and effectiveness (Nevins-Bennett 2016). Moreover, Nevins-Bennett,(2016) defined production deviance as "Any conscious counterproductive acts brought about by the intentional behavior of an organizational member which violates significant organizational norms of' acceptable production level in a manner which' is contrary to the interest of' the organization that harms or intend to harm the organization delineating the minimal quality and' quantity' of work to be accomplished and by extension resulting in a decline in organizational performance and 'profitability. In UK, estimated \$600 million loss of productivity per year due to web- surfing reported at workplace (Taylor, 2007).

Sabotage

Sabotage workplace deviance has been of interest to a broad range of researchers and Practitioners (Ambrose, Seabright & Schmink 2002). Sabotage is important dimension of deviant workplace behavior (DWB) which closely related to production deviance (Spector, et al. (2006). However, production deviance is a passive whereas sabotage is active approach, but in fact, both act are knotted theoretically(Robinson & Bennet, 1995). Production deviance and sabotage are reflecting the two different kinds of behaviors, firstly, it indicates the not to do a task or do not task correctly and secondly, intentionally damaging something (Gruys & Sackett 2003; Robinson & Bennet, 1995).

Corruption/Kickback

Corruption is a most serious dimension of deviance behavior prevalent in Pakistan at all levels like other factors of deviant workplace behavior (DWB) (Bashir et al., 2012; Islam, 2004). Accepting Kickback is another type of property deviance (Robbins & Bennett, 1995). In the words of (Bashir et al., 2012) accepting kickback is a type of corruption and it an important dimension of deviant workplace behavior in public organization. Kickback has negative impact on public organizations of countless developed and developing countries like Pakistan (Bashir et al. 2011). Even though hard evidence of corruption's incidence is difficult to attain, however, different surveys and reports, historical accounts and case studies indicate that corruption/kickback is pervasive in Pakistan at all levels (Pellegrini, 2007). Corruption/kickback has become a common way of life in Pakistan (Islam, 2004), therefore corruption made institutes or organizations in Pakistan extremely inefficient (Abbasi, 2011). This has led to a general impression that practice of corruption has increased in volume over time and there is less evidence that people feel guilty about it (Javed et al. 2014). The prevalence of corruption on such a wide scale can be stated through apt expression by Pakistani researcher Ehtisham, (2009) "From policemen on the beat to highest ranks, from legal clerks to judges, from minor revenue officials to senior administrators, from storekeepers to high-ranking engineers, all government and private agencies are involved in corruption."

Transformational Leadership

In every organization, the role of leadership is indispensable (Maher & Youssef, 2016). Leaders play a vital role to manage employee's dysfunctional or deviant behaviour at workplace (Maher & Youssef, 2016) and success of every business depends upon effective leadership of the organization, without appropriate leadership no one organization either public or private can survive (Maher & Youssef 2016). Leadership is the process having influence on subordinate employees at workplace. Leader motivates the employee to achieve specific targeted goals and objective of the organization and maintain coordination and cooperation for development of the organization (Yukl, 1994) and enhance the employee's productivity and creativity (Fry, 2003). Leadership is a complex concept (Zhang 2016). Leadership may refer to those who occupy the highest positions in various organizations or it may refer to those who possess certain leadership characteristics or qualities (Silva, 2014). Academic consensus of Silva (2014), identified and understands that leadership is basically a circumstantial relationship between a leader and his or her followers. Several views have been expressed on leadership style in research by different researchers (Puni, Agyemang & Asamoah 2016).

Generally, there are number of style of leaderships are studies in research such as autocratic leadership style, democratic style of leadership, Laissez-fair style of leadership, transactional leadership, and transformational leadership style. Autocratic leadership style make decision on the basis of power and authority and determine policies, procedures for achieving goals and objective and believes mainly on implementation of the rules and regulation and control on rewards and authority (Punie, ofei & Okoe, 2013). The second, style of leadership in which leader make decision to get involve the subordinate and helps to develop individual's skills and promote team work friendliness, helpfulness and encouragement of participation (Puni, et al. 2016). The third, style of leadership is laissez-fair leadership which is basically "non- leadership style" because the leader has no influence over the group members (Bass, 1965). Laissez-fair leadership style is an effective style, when employees are highly educated, experienced and skilled (Yukl, 1994) or when employees have pride in their work and derived to do work successfully on their own (Yukl, 1994). Such leaders achieve goals and objectives are only established when necessary or required and to avoid decision making and unnecessary communications (Puni et al. 2016). The fourth style of leadership is transactional leadership. Transactional leadership focus to motivate or inspire their followers through the system of reward and punishment and focuses on increasing the efficiency of the employee (Bass, 1965). Transactional leadership style is management of expectations and allowances or rewards. This type of leadership maintains the status quo and more concerned to follow the existing rules and regulations and procedure of the operation (Puni, et al. 2016; Pradhan & Pradhan, 2014). Transformational leadership is a one type of leadership and differs from another type of leadership style name of transactional leadership style; this is an expression of ethical guidelines and leaders' noble intensions (Pradhan, & Pradhan 2014). Moreover, on the basis of moral influence on the followers' transformational leadership differs from other leadership styles especially transactional leadership. It raises different level of morality and values on the leader and the followers too (Pradhan, & Pradhan 2014). A study of Bass (1985; 1987) formed that transformational leadership is not myth but reality and explained transformational leadership style in term of to judge the influence on follower. Burns, (1978) defined transformational leadership style "occurs when the leaders and led both engage with each other in such a way that both raises each other to higher level of motivational and morality." Furthermore, Transformational leadership comprising of four components consist of charisma, inspiration motivation, intellectual stimulation and individual consideration. Bass, (1987) further explain four dimensions of transformational leadership as the first; charisma is a behaviour which produces strong emotions, in follower as well as leaders' identification. The second, inspiration to articulate is a strong persuasive vision to help out the subordinate's efforts at workplace. The third, intellectual stimulation is referred to behaviour that enhances the awareness of problem as well as motivate followers to sight the problem from narrative perspective and the fourth, "individualized consideration" is another component transformation leadership to provide lending sport and guideline to followers.

Relationship between Transformational leadership and Deviant Workplace Behavior

The relationship between transformational leadership and deviant workplace behavior is presumed as independent variable is assumed to predispose some individual to engage in deviant behavior. The deviant behaviors are likely to be effected by the transformational leadership because transformational leadership .The presumed dimension of transformational leadership is predictors to deviance. It is hypothesized that there is negative association between deviant workplace behaviors of employees. And Social learning theory and Social Exchange Theory are supporting the relationship to predict the deviant workplace behavior. the present study examines transformational leadership and presumed transformational leadership moderator variable among the individual and organizational factors and deviance behaviour at workplace. It is generally accepted quality of leadership, that the leadership can play very important role in either boosting or diminishing such negative behaviour (Kurkand, 1995). However, transformational leadership style may serve to moderate the relationship between factors and deviant workplace behaviour (Pradhan & Pradhan, 2014).

This study forecast that transformational leadership is helpful to modify the association between moral disengagement (deviant workplace Behaviour) in different customs (Hystad, Mearns, & Eid, 2014). Transformational leadership style gives attentions to followers (Bass, 1998; Avolio & Bass, 1999). This vision factor of transformational leadership made use of motivating to employees (Pradhan & Pradhan, 2014). In this manner and process of transforming, Transformal leaders listen to their subordinate employees and try to figure out values and provision they have (Bass et al., 2003). The study presumed transformational leadership is predictors to deviance at workplace and hypothesized that there is negative association between deviant workplace behaviors of employees. And social learning theory and social exchange theory is supporting the relationship to predict the deviant workplace behaviour, SET explains the positive relationship between personal/individual value and organizational value in response of exchange (Fayyaz & Alasani 2015). Transformational leadership style always tries to protect their followers' against deviant behaviours and toxic at workplace (Hepworth & Towler 2004). In the words of Pradhan and Pradhan, (2014) "it is generally accepted element among the research scholars that quality and type of leadership can play vital role to boost or diminish negative behaviours". Transformational leadership promotes positive culture in the organization and hypothesized on the base of above discussion such as.

H1: There is significant negative relationship between Transformational Leadership and deviant workplace behavior.

Theoretical Framework

Deviant workplace Behavior is presumed as Dependent Variable and

Transformational Leadership is presumed as Independent Variable

Methodology

The purpose of the present study is going to investigate the impact of Transformational leadership on deviant workplace behavior of employees in Pakistani public organizations.

This research design covers type of explanatory research that is help to investigate the impact of changes in existing phenomena and particularly focus on specific problem to explain the patterns of relationship among the different variables such as independent variables, dependent variable. Data collection process has been used cross-sectional via survey questionnaire. Furthermore, as this study focus on cross-sectional research compared

observation the different variable at same time such as gender, marital status, education, experience, tenure and level of job or marginality position. Quantitative approach was utilized in this research to collect and analysis of data because the results of quantitative research are relatively independent.

As the object of the preset study is to investigate the impact of individual factors i.e. Big five personality and dark triad contributing the deviant workplace behavior working in public organizations and moderating role transformational leadership, therefore the target population for this study is consisted of 20 public organization i.e. universities, autonomous bodies, special institutions and attached departments of the province of the Punjab, Pakistan. Sample from population of employees will be determined on base of guidelines presented by Krejcie & Morgan, (1970) from each public organization included in population. The current study of will be conducted in 20 educational public organizations government of the Punjab, Pakistan based province capital, Lahore. On the basis of information available at website of the Government of the Punjab (www.punjab.gov.pk) there are 40 provincial departments, 108 Attached department, 152 Autonomous bodies and 12 Special institutions of the Govt. of the Punjab are working in the province of Punjab Pakistan from 152 and autonomous and special institution 100 related to education from them 20 organizations related to education and training sector were selected for study because education aligned organization can get the benefit of the outcome of the study. The reason behind chose these public organizations is that they all are provincial headquarter bases and there working cover whole province the Punjab territory. Sekaran, (2003) asserts that stratified sampling design is comparatively more efficient in the case of heterogeneous population for meeting the objectives of the study, the Stratification of the population. Cluster sampling for the selection of organizations, the purposive, non-probability sampling technique the most suitable for the current study (Sekaran & Boguee, 2010). In the selection of organization, only autonomous bodies and special institution who have their head office /head quarter at provincial capital Lahore but their working is speared in different region throughout the Punjab will be chosen as geographical area for conducting research. Self-administrated questionnaire was used to collect information from respondent i.e. employees of public organizations situated in Pakistan.

Measures

In order to conduct survey a self-administrated questionnaire has been used as instrument and the closed ended type of questionnaire was used to conduct the current study. The respondents were only asked to tick the answer given, from 1 to 5. The questionnaire was adopted from previous researcher work of eminent scholars. Deviant workplace behavior in public sector organizations has been measured by 7 dimensions scale of deviance workplace behavior, stated 76 subscale that can be divided as 4 sub scale to measure "Sabotage" (Spector, et al. 2006); 4 sub scale to measure "Withdrawal" (Spector, et al., 2006); 04 sub scale to measure "Theft" (Spector, Fox, Penney, et al., 2006); 3 sub scale to measure to "Property deviance" 5 sub scale to "Misuse of time and resources" (Bashir et al. 2012); 5 subscale to measure to "Kickbacks /Corruption" (Bashir et al., 2012); 18-sub scale to measure to "Abuse to others/Bullying" (Spector, et al. 2006). In survey questionnaire, this was measured at Five Likert scales that contain (1 to 5) such as strongly disagree, disagree, to strongly agree. 20 items of transformational leadership was used to measure with help of items from the Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire (MLQ Form 5X; Bass & Avolio, 1995). In survey questionnaire, for this section Five Likert- scales that contain (1 to 5) such as strongly disagree, to strongly agree was used. Research instrument are explained in this section. Most of the instruments are adopted from earlier research studies having acceptable range of reliabilities calculated by Cronbach s Alpha.

Data Analysis

In order to data analysis, Structural Equation Model (SEM) is used generally in social and behavioral sciences (Hair, Hult, Ringle & Sarstedt 2013). As the SEM is largely applied in the behavioral and behavioral science field to assess the causal modeling of complex and multivariate datasets in which there are compound measures of proposed constructs (Hair, et al. 2013). Applying SEM in the field of social sciences i.e. management and organizational behavior has considerably increased because of the presence of a number of packages of software that perform SEM (Hair et al. 2013). SEM techniques is used to analysis the data of present study

because is very general modeling technique contained combination of path analysis, regression analysis as well as factor analysis. And the focus in SEM is usually on theoretical construct.

Results and Discussion

Table No. 1

Descriptive Statistics

Variables	Mean	S.D	Skewness
Organizational Injustice	3.0927	0.71399	-.213
Transformational leadership	3.0203	0.76921	-.645

Table 1 shows the values of mean, SD and skewness of the data. The values of mean are in range of 3.02 to 3.09. The values of standard deviation are in the range of 0.11 to 0.76 while the values of skewness are in limit of -1 to +1. The skewness results have confirmed that data is normal. As all objective variables have been proved normal, so the analysis can move forward.

Table No. 2

Model Fitness Measures

	CMIN/DF	GFI	CFI	RMSEA	IFI
Model 1	3.008	0.911	0.997	.029	0.972

The above mentioned table showed Fit indices values for current research which are Normed Chi-square=3.008, GFI =0.911, CFI =0.997, IFI =0.972, and RMSEA = 0.029 all these results are within acceptance region so it means that measurement model is fit and it can be relied upon. For an instance, the threshold value of RMSEA must be lesser than 0.08 and it is 0.02 in case of this research.

Table No. 3

Psychometric Properties

Constructs	α	CR	AVE	MaxR(H)	WD	TL
WD	0.899	0.911	0.596	0.903	0.654	
TL	0.823	0.921	0.597	0.909	0.544	0.666

Table 3 has mentioned the results of psychometric properties. Threshold value for composite reliability must be greater than 0.8, the results shown in above table are meeting this criteria because all the values of CR are in the range of 0.91 to 0.92 which are greater than 0.8. While the value of AVE must be greater than 0.5, the results depicted in the above table showed that all the values of AVE is greater than 0.5. Hence the convergent validity and reliability is proved from the results. Fornell and Larcker (1981) says that to test the discriminant validity, it is considered essential that values of square root for AVE should be more analogize with correlation values of its own and other variables. The results shown in the above mentioned Table for square root AVE describing values in diagonal and all bold values in diagonal are meeting criteria which confirm the discriminant validity. Values of Cronbach alpha are greater than 0.7 for all variables which means that data is reliable.

Table No. 4

Structured Equation Modeling

Relationships	Unstandardized β	Standardized β	S.E	C.R	P
TL→WD	.312	-.294	.173	2.007	***

Note: *= $p < 0.05$, **= $p < 0.01$, ***= $p < 0.001$.

Table No. 4 is showing the values of standardized regression weights obtained after running structural equation modeling. The results have concluded that transformational leadership can decrease the workplace deviance by 29% and the results are significant too as P-value is lesser than 0.05.

Future Directions

Although, the present study has provided support for a number of the hypothesized relationship among the exogenous, endogenous and intervening variables, the results have to be interpreted under consideration of the some study limitations:

The first, this study assumes and adopts a cross-sectional research design which does not allow casual inferences to be made from the population. Therefore, a longitudinal research design in future needs to be considered to measure the theoretical constructs at different points in time to confirm the findings of the present study. Secondly, the present adopts a non-probability sampling technique i.e. quota sampling in which all elements of the target population were not captured, as such the extent to which sample size represents the entire population cannot be known. The use of quota sampling has limited the extent to which the findings of the study can be generalized to the population. Thirdly, in present study, it is possible that the respondents belongs to Public sector organizations might have under reported their deviant behaviour on closed ended survey questionnaire. Therefore, in future, researcher may wish to employ other strategies i.e. direct observations, interview, case study etc. to assess deviance workplace behaviour of public sector organizations.

Fourthly, in the present study, it is pertinent to mention that the deviant workplace behaviour reported was subjective. The outcome of the present research demonstrates that subjective data is valid and reliable for assessing deviant workplace behaviour. Therefore, in future the outcome of the present research may be replicated by using objective measures of deviant workplace behaviour.

Fifthly, the outcome of present study offers quite limited generalizability because it focused mainly on employees who are working in public organizations located in Lahore the provincial headquarter of Punjab, Pakistan. Therefore, in future it is essential, in order to generalize the finding to include employees who are working in the other Province of Pakistan.

The lastly, it is important to note that there was significant moderating effect of transformational leadership between Individual factors dark triad personality traits and deviant workplace behaviours found. Therefore, in future, further research is desirable to investigate such type of mediator effects with other moderating variables.

Conclusion

The current study has provided additional indication and evidence to the growing body of knowledge regarding the impact of transformational leadership and deviant workplace behaviour. Despite of some limitations of present study, the results from the study lend support to the theoretical propositions, key objectives and answered research questions. In spite of, there have been number of studies carried out to examining the underlying antecedents and causes of deviant workplace behaviour. However, this study addressed the theoretical gap by incorporating transformational leadership as independent variable to control deviant workplace behaviour.

The present study also lends support to theoretical and empirical framework for the moderating role of transformational leadership on the relationship between individual and and deviant workplace behaviour. This study has also managed to evaluate how transformational leadership theoretically moderates the relationships between the independent and dependent variables. Furthermore, the theoretical framework of this study has also

added to the domain Breach of Psychological contract theory by examining the influence of individual factors i.e. big five personality traits and dark triad personality on deviant workplace behaviour.

The outcome of this study also provides important practical implication to the head of the institutions, managers, and organization too. In spite of the some limitations of the present study, several recommendations, directions and guidelines for future research has been drawn in this study.

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